

Body-Oriented Gesture Generation System for Medical Interpreter Robots Based on Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback

Tung T. Ngo¹[0009-0004-0065-8600], Emma Murphy¹[0000-0001-6738-3067], Conor McGinn²[0000-0001-9019-6809], and Robert Ross¹[0000-0001-7088-273X]

¹ Technological University Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

² Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

Abstract. Medical interpreters are crucial in facilitating communication between healthcare stakeholders who speak different languages. Body-oriented gestures convey critical information essential for accurate and high-quality interpretation in healthcare settings. This study introduces a body-oriented gesture generation system designed for medical interpreter robots based on reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF). The system allows robots to interpret more naturally and improve over time through interactions with humans. By adopting a human-centered development approach, we tailor our system to address the actual needs of healthcare stakeholders.

Keywords: Medical Interpreter Robot · Human-Centered Development · Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback.

1 Introduction

Research indicates that non-verbal communication plays a crucial role in effective medical interpretation in healthcare settings. Both gaze and body-oriented gesture significantly influence patient inclusion in interpreter-mediated consultations [4]. A significant proportion of healthcare stakeholders’ gestures convey information not expressed through speech [2], highlighting their importance beyond verbal communication. Furthermore, gestures made during pain descriptions offer additional insights into patients’ pain experiences without hindering their comprehension of spoken information [8]. These findings emphasize the importance of body-oriented gestures to medical interpreter robots.

Most existing gesture generation studies have focused on co-speech gestures in everyday conversation, rather than in healthcare contexts. Several works examining gesture generation in dyadic interactions have emerged through the GENE Challenge [5]. State-of-the-art methods have employed generative models such as GANs [6], VQ-VAEs [11], and diffusion models [9,10,1], achieving notable advancements in speech-gesture animation. However, these models have been primarily trained on datasets representing general speaking scenarios [7], such as casual dialogues and news broadcasts. Notably, body-oriented gestures

specific to healthcare settings remain largely unexplored. Moreover, current generative approaches lack the ability to learn from or adapt to real-time interactions with humans, limiting their responsiveness and personalization in dynamic environments.

In this work, we propose the Body-Oriented Gesture Generation based on Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (**BOGRH**) framework for medical interpreter robots. Unlike conventional approaches that synthesize gestures directly from speech, BOGRH utilizes both speech-generated gestures and user gestures as inputs to teach a reinforcement learning agent to perform body-oriented gestures. A reinforcement learning algorithm enables the agent to improve over time through interactions with humans, incorporating positive reinforcement for effective gestures and negative feedback for corrections, ensuring the robot’s gestures align closely with human cues.

2 Human-Centered Development

To develop a medical interpreter robot tailored to the actual needs of healthcare stakeholders, this study uses the human-centered development (HCD) approach, prioritizing the insights and experiences of end-users throughout the development process. Semi-structured, one-on-one interviews have been conducted with healthcare professionals (e.g., physicians, nurses, and medical staff) and patients representing diverse backgrounds to explore communication challenges. Interview questions focus on identifying barriers to effective communication and important gestures during clinical interactions. Participants have been recruited purposively to ensure representation across roles, languages, and healthcare contexts. Interviews have been audio-recorded, transcribed, pseudonymized, filtered, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and critical themes. Coding will be performed iteratively, with initial codes grouped into higher-order themes reflecting systemic, interpersonal, and technological challenges in cross-linguistic healthcare communication. This analysis will inform the identification of key functional requirements for the robot, such as real-time translation accuracy, natural gestures, and user-friendly interfaces. By grounding the design process in the lived experiences of stakeholders, the HCD methodology ensures the resulting robot addresses practical needs.

3 Medical Interpreter Robot System

Our proposed system is shown in Fig. 1. First, the user’s speech \mathcal{S}_{user} is translated into \mathcal{S}_{tran} by the speech-to-speech translation model *OpenAI Whisper*¹. Next, *DiffuseStyleGesture* [10] processes this translated speech \mathcal{S}_{tran} to generate corresponding gestures, which are then saved in BioVision Hierarchy (BVH) file format. These gestures are then converted into an array $\mathcal{G}_{gen} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 12}$, representing the Pepper robot’s 12 joint angles over n timestamps. Simultaneously, the

¹ <https://github.com/openai/whisper>

system employs *MediaPipe Pose Landmarker*² to detect pose landmarks from video data captured by the robot’s camera. The extracted keypoints are then transformed into a recognized gesture array $\mathcal{G}_{reg} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 12}$. Finally, an RLHF agent utilizes both \mathcal{G}_{reg} and \mathcal{G}_{gen} to learn a policy for generating body-oriented gestures tailored for the robot.

Fig. 1. System overview of the Body-Oriented Gesture Generation based on Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (BOGRH) framework for medical interpreter robots.

4 Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback

Fig. 2 illustrates our proposed algorithm to train the Pepper robot to perform body-oriented gestures using RLHF. First, a neural network is developed to take as input the generated gesture \mathcal{G}_{gen} and the recognized gesture \mathcal{G}_{reg} , and to output a new gesture \mathcal{G}_a . This model is optimized using a combination of loss functions as in (1). These loss functions compare the new gesture with the generated and recognized gestures based on statistical metrics. We apply the Contrastive Preference Learning [3] algorithm to train the RLHF agent. This algorithm directly learns a preference model without using a reward function, thus more efficient. Finally, the RLHF framework leverages real human preferences to fine-tune the gesture policy, ensuring that Pepper learns to produce gestures that align closely with human expectations.

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \lambda_h \mathcal{L}_{Huber} + \lambda_p \mathcal{L}_{phy} + \lambda_k \mathcal{L}_{KLD} \quad (1)$$

² https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/vision/pose_landmarker

Fig. 2. Our proposed reinforcement learning from human feedback algorithm.

To train our proposed algorithm, the data construction process involves multiple stages. First, a gesture dataset is curated using the public Macleod’s clinical training videos³, providing demonstrations of expert-level actions and body language in medical contexts. This dataset serves as the foundation for supervised learning. Next, a synthetic preference dataset is generated by sampling and ranking outputs from a base model, often using heuristics or pre-trained models to approximate human-like preferences. This synthetic data helps scale up training before involving real annotators. Finally, real-human preferences are collected by having human evaluators compare pairs of model outputs and select the more appropriate one based on task relevance and alignment with expert behavior. These human-labeled comparisons are essential for fine-tuning the reward model, which is used to guide the reinforcement learning process toward more desirable behaviors.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have introduced a new framework for medical interpreter robots based on Reinforcement learning from Human Feedback. Our framework enables robots to learn and improve their communicative behaviors through ongoing interaction with humans. Grounded in a human-centered development approach, our system prioritizes the needs and feedback of real healthcare stakeholders throughout the design and training process. This capability is particularly critical in healthcare settings, where gestures must be contextually appropriate and responsive to patient needs.

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³ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLGSEsMFkgqnxC3Yvkq7_sdfUszaRvIpr

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